

Seven Readings of the Qur'an (Kitab al-Sab'ah fi al-Qira'at) by Ibn Mujahid

By Ian VanderMeulen, Kalamazoo College

Entry tags: Qur'anic commentary (Tafsir), Religious Group, Text, Scholastic text, Islamic Traditions, Fiqh

Text by Ahmed Ibn Musa Ibn al-Abbas Ibn Mujahid which authorized and helped canonize seven acceptable vocalized readings (qira'at) of the Qur'an, Islam's revealed text.

Date Range: 900 CE - 936 CE

Region: Baghdad, 'Abbasid capital

Region tags: Iraq

Ibn Mujahid likely produced the Kitab al-Sab'ah in Baghdad, the capital of the 'Abbasid caliphate at the time he was working for them, but the text has subsequently circulated much more widely

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Nasser, Shady Hekmat. *Transmission of the Variant Readings of the Qur'an: The Problem of Tawatur and the Emergence of Shawadhhdh* (Leiden: Brill, 2012).
- Source 2: Nasser, Shady Hekmat. "The Two-Rāwī Canon before and after ad-Dānī (d. 444/1052-3): The Role of Abū ṭ-Ṭayyib Ibn Chalbūn (d. 389/998) and the Qayrawān/Andalus School in Creating the Two-Rāwī Canon." *Oriens* 41.1-02 (2013): 41-75.
- Source 3: Melchert, Christopher. "Ibn Mujahid and the Establishment of Seven Qur'anic Readings," *Studia Islamica*, 91 (2000): 5-22.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-2/kiraa-SIM_4383?s.num=420&s.start=420
- Source 1 Description: Paret, R., "Ḳirā'at", in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition*, Edited by: P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs. Consulted online on 13 December 2022

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: Kitab al-Sab'ah fi al-Qira'at is available in at least one modern, edited print edition and numerous manuscript copies

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Inked

–with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Specify type of paper

–Specify: Unknown

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Unknown

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: Kitab al-Sab'ah fi al-Qira'at is available in at least one modern, edited print edition and numerous manuscript copies

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

— No

Notes: This is debatable, depending on how one conceives of religious "leadership," but there is, in theory, a division of labor and balance of power between the temporal authority of the caliph and the authority of those who interpret religious texts for moral and legal purposes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

— Yes

Notes: Office of the Caliph and religious specialists officially separate, but many religious scholars also served bureaucratic functions

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Present full-time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Notes: Religious scholars in 'Abbasid caliphate overwhelmingly male, but there are known cases of important female scholars

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Though the elite Islamic scholars who would have been the intended audience of this text would have been limited, exact numbers are difficult if not impossible to estimate. However, the author Ibn Mujahid himself was said to have had as many as 800 in his own "study circle" alone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Proselytization in Islam is widespread, generally, but since the text does not circumscribe a specific sub-"group," the text itself is unlikely to be associated with any proselytizing activity

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Text is written in classical Arabic, which is derived from Qur'anic Arabic, but is slightly different and nonetheless does not carry the status of "scripture" the way the Qur'an does

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Notes: This is debatable, depending on how one conceives of religious "leadership," but there is, in theory, a division of labor and balance of power between the temporal authority of the caliph and the authority of those who interpret religious texts for moral and legal purposes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional

networks?

– Yes

Notes: Office of the Caliph and religious specialists officially separate, but many religious scholars also served bureaucratic functions

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Present full-time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Notes: Religious scholars in 'Abbasid caliphate overwhelmingly male, but there are known cases of important female scholars

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Text is written in classical Arabic, which is derived from Qur'anic Arabic, but is slightly different and nonetheless does not carry the status of "scripture" the way the Qur'an does

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Though the elite Islamic scholars who would have been the intended audience of this text would have been limited, exact numbers are difficult if not impossible to estimate. However, the author Ibn Mujahid himself was said to have had as many as 800 in his own "study circle" alone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Proselytization in Islam is widespread, generally, but since the text does not circumscribe a specific sub-"group," the text itself is unlikely to be associated with any proselytizing activity

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Normative Islamic tradition makes certain spirit-body distinctions but those don't appear to be treated in this text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Most Islamic scholarly texts begin by appealing to God that the author's attempt at bestowing knowledge will be favorable. Beyond that there appears to be very little reference to the "supernatural" in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Index

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: Although the text certain helps establish norms, these relate almost exclusively to ritual practice (i.e. reciting the Qur'an)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Not a single chain of authority, but rather unique chains of authority for each (eponymous) reading or qira'a

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: Islamic eschatology is rich, generally, but does not appear to be relevant to this text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear whether text itself calls for 'Abbasid state intervention, but Melchert (2000) begins his article with the claim that at least two reciters contemporary with Ibn Mujahid "were famously tried for reciting unacceptable variants," suggesting that the text (or Ibn Mujahid) was at least consulted as the basis of legal action.

Reference: Melchert, Christopher. "Ibn Mujahid and the Establishment of Seven Qur'anic Readings". *Studia Islamica* 91 (2000): 5-22.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Cultural with religious implications?

– I don't know

Notes: The text itself is concerned with authorizing the seven qira'at based on their scholarly trains of transmission. However, preferences for a particular reading against others have taken on geographical dimensions which, in the modern period, has resulted in certain "cultural" associations with particular readings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Other

–Other [specify]: Kitab al-Sab'ah fi al-qira'at is generally considered part of the Qur'anic sciences ('ulum al-qur'an), a sub-discipline of traditional Islamic scholarship concerning the Qur'an's revelation, codification, recitation, interpretation, (physical) handling, and other issues

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: Recitation of the Qur'an is common during funerary proceedings, but that is only one of its many ritual uses, and the ritual context does not seem to be relevant to the text's purposes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: Regular prayer is proscribed in Islam, all the more so for the elite scholars who are the primary intended audience of the text, but the text does not lay that out as a precondition for reading it

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: There may be an implication, however, that adherence to one of the seven readings (or none at all) helps establish each as a sort of "school," thus suggesting forms of sociality beyond ritual, proper

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Cultural with religious implications?

– I don't know

Notes: The text itself is concerned with authorizing the seven qira'at based on their scholarly trains of transmission. However, preferences for a particular reading against others have taken on geographical dimensions which, in the modern period, has resulted in certain "cultural" associations with particular readings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Other

– Other [specify]: Kitab al-Sab'ah fi al-qira'at is generally considered part of the Qur'anic sciences ('ulum al-qur'an), a sub-discipline of traditional Islamic scholarship concerning the Qur'an's revelation, codification, recitation, interpretation, (physical) handling, and other issues

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Index

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Not a single chain of authority, but rather unique chains of authority for each (eponymous) reading or qira'a

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear whether text itself calls for 'Abbasid state intervention, but Melchert (2000) begins his article with the claim that at least two reciters contemporary with Ibn Mujahid "were famously tried for reciting unacceptable variants," suggesting that the text (or Ibn Mujahid) was at least consulted as the basis of legal action.

Reference: Melchert, Christopher. "Ibn Mujahid and the Establishment of Seven Qur'anic Readings". *Studia Islamica* 91 (2000): 5-22.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Normative Islamic tradition makes certain spirit-body distinctions but those don't appear to be treated in this text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: Recitation of the Qur'an is common during funerary proceedings, but that is only one of its many ritual uses, and the ritual context does not seem to be relevant to the text's purposes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Most Islamic scholarly texts begin by appealing to God that the author's attempt at bestowing knowledge will be favorable. Beyond that there appears to be very little reference to the "supernatural" in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: Islamic eschatology is rich, generally, but does not appear to be relevant to this text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: Although the text certainly helps establish norms, these relate almost exclusively to ritual practice

(i.e. reciting the Qur'an)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: Regular prayer is proscribed in Islam, all the more so for the elite scholars who are the primary intended audience of the text, but the text does not lay that out as a precondition for reading it

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: There may be an implication, however, that adherence to one of the seven readings (or none at all) helps establish each as a sort of "school," thus suggesting forms of sociality beyond ritual, proper

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: I am unaware of any cases involving the destruction of this text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: I am unaware of any cases involving the destruction of this text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Baghdad

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: I don't know, Melchert, Christopher. "Ibn Mujahid and the Establishment of Seven Qur'anic

Readings". *Studia Islamica* 91 (2000): 5-22.